

Importance of Training on Agricultural Mechanization among Farmers in Saki-West Local Government Area

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Abstract

Poor Farmers' training on agricultural mechanization has reduced production of crops in Nigeria. This study therefore examined importance of training on agricultural mechanization among Farmers in Saki-West Local Government Area. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 65 Farmers in the study area. Data were collected using interview schedule. Descriptive statistical tools were used. The least importance of agricultural training of respondents was agricultural training helps farmers to know the right machinery to use/hire and it includes strongly agree (0.00%), agree (7.69), neutral (21.54%), disagree (29.23%) and disagree (41.54%). The most prominent perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery was usage of agricultural machinery are too expensive and it includes strongly agree (15.38%), agree (41.54), neutral (36.92%), disagree (6.15%) and disagree (0.00%). It was concluded that most of the farmers do not know the right machinery to use. It was recommended that agricultural extension agents should educate farmers on the right machinery to use.

Keywords: Agricultural mechanization, extension agents, farmers, machinery and training

1. INTRODUCTION

Most of the farm women use traditional tools and implements since a long time and majority of the farm women also faced difficulties & problem in using traditional tools and implements (Abimbola, 2014; Adebayo, 2015). Majority of the farm women agreed that “Manual bund former” and “Fertilizer broadcaster” would not affect their traditional norms/ values and society can permit them to use it (Verma, 2005). Tubular maize Sheller, hanging type double screen grain cleaner, groundnut decorticator, manual twin wheel hoe and serrated sickle showed decrease in physiological cost of work of farm women and increased work out put compared to conventional method.

According to Abimbola (2014) there is need of more site-specific use of farm machinery for enhancement of agricultural production and livelihood security. Training and demonstration is an effective tool for the transfer of technology (Abubakar, 2015). They have also asserted that training is the most singular factor affecting individuals’ attitude, productivity, improvement and minimization of risks (Adama, 2015). Training to be an important paradigm of agricultural extension for the transfer of technology, skill, knowledge and attitude to farmers to develop their competency. Since agricultural technologies and practices are constantly changing, training plays a crucial role in keeping the farmers abreast with these advancements in the agriculture sector (FAO, 2011).

Adequate training is essential for farmers to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills in different aspects of farming (FAO, 2014). This is more important for the farmers interested in farm machinery with the unique situation of North East. Keeping these in view, an attempt was made to assess the performance of training with the help of a structure evaluation sheet.

Nigeria is blessed with 98.3million hectares of arable landmass but only 35 per cent of the arable land is under actual cultivation (FAO, 2014). Despite the high proportion of cultivated landmass relative to the total available space, food production to feed the teeming populace has remained a mirage. Land tenure system: The types of land ownership in Nigeria do not allow the use of farm machines. High cost of mechanization fee. Farmer’s adoption process rate in using farm mechanization. Generating of funds for Equipment acquisition source of loan e.g.

cooperative, microfinance. Maintenance/ High cost of Maintenance Poverty of farmers: Some farmers are poor and cannot afford to own farm machines.

Inadequate machines and facilities: Are not enough where they are available. Bad nature of land (Topography): The topography of West African lands are rough and too bad for mechanization Soil types: the soil type of West African do not suit mechanization and suitable machines have not been produced. Inadequate spare parts: Most of the machines spare parts are imported and not easily found to repair damaged parts. Inadequate operators: Train people to handle and repair these machines are scarcely found. Scattered farm land/fragmentation: scattered farm lands or fragmented are not conducive for mechanization.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Identify the importance of Agricultural training of respondents.
2. Assess the perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study was carried out in Saki West Local Government. Saki town (alternatively spelled Shaki) is in the northern part of Oyo state, western Nigeria. It lies close to the wellspring of the Ofiki River (the central feeder of the Ogun River), around 40 miles (60 km) from the Benin line. Initially part of the Oyo domain, Saki turned into a Yoruba displaced person settlement after the obliteration in 1835 of Old Oyo (Katunga), 70 miles (113 km) east-upper east, by Muslim Fulani champions. By the mid-1860s the Yoruba Mission had set up an Anglican church in the town. In Saki, the wet season is harsh and cloudy, the dry season is humid and mostly overcast, and it is hot all year. Throughout the year, the temperature regularly shifts from 20°C to 34°C and is seldom goes below 17°C or above 37°C. Saki town is inhabited by the Yoruba people an ethnic group that occupies western Africa, essentially the nations of Nigeria, Benin, and Togo. Saki is located in the northern part of Oyo state. There are two ways to get into Shaki town: by air and by bus. You can go by air by taking a direct flight from the Lagos Airport to Ilorin Airport which takes 45 min, you will need to use a connecting vehicle usually a shared taxi to get to Shaki town.

The population for this study consisted of all Farmers in Saki West Local Government Area of Oyo State.

The study randomly selected 5 wards out of 11 agricultural wards in Saki West. Which are Saki and Asabari Agricultural ward. From the selected wards, 20% of the villages were randomly selected from each wards. In Ekokan ward: Wasangari, Budo Ali, and Gbepakan, were randomly selected the number of registered Agricultural Mechanization under the umbrella of AFAN (ALL FARMERS ASSOCIATION OF NIGERIA) will be used for the study. The registered farmer constituted 650. However, 10% of the registered farmers will constitute the sample size. Thus, the sample size will be 65 farmers.

Descriptive Statistical Tools that were used include frequency counts, percentages and means. These were used to describe the importance of Agricultural training and perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery.

.3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Importance of agricultural training of respondents

In Table 1, importance of agricultural training of respondents were presented. The least importance of agricultural training of respondents was agricultural training helps farmers to know the right machinery to use/hire and it includes; strongly agree (0.00%), agree (7.69%), neutral (21.54%), disagree (29.23%) and disagree (41.54%). This implies that most of the farmers do not know the right machinery to use.

Table 1: Importance of agricultural training of respondents

Importance of Agricultural Training of Respondents	Frequently	Percent
Agricultural training helps farmers to know the right machinery to use/hire		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	5	7.69
Neutral	14	21.54
Strongly Disagree	19	29.23
Disagree	27	41.54
Its knowledge could make farm work less laborious		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	42	64.62
Neutral	15	23.08
Strongly Disagree	8	12.31
Disagree	0	
Its knowledge could make farm enterprise more profitable		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	5	7.69
Neutral	28	43.08
Strongly Disagree	15	23.08
Disagree	17	26.15
Its knowledge could make farm work faster		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	47	72.31
Neutral	14	12.54
Strongly Disagree	4	6.15
Disagree	0	0.-00
The training is a waste of time		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	28	43.08
Neutral	19	29.23
Strongly Disagree	4	6.15
Disagree	14	21.54

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Table 1: Importance of agricultural training of respondents Cont.

Importance of Agricultural Training of Respondents	Frequently	Percent
The traditional way of farming were older and better than the modern method been taught by the extension agents		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	19	29.77
Neutral	33	50.77
Strongly Disagree	0	0.00
Disagree	13	20.00
The training is for only highly educated farmers		
Strongly Agree	9	13.85
Agree	28	43.88
Neutral	19	29.23
Strongly Disagree	4	6.15
Disagree	5	7.69
The training is for only large scale farmers		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	4	6.15
Neutral	29	44.62
Strongly Disagree	10	15.38
Disagree	22	33.65

Source: Field survey, 2023.

Perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery

In Table 2, perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery were presented. The most prominent perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery was usage of agricultural machinery are too expensive and it includes; strongly agree (15.38%), agree (41.54),neutral (36.92%), disagree (6.15%) and disagree (0.00%). This implies that most of the farmers could not afford the use of agricultural mechanization due to its ex expensiveness.

Table 2: Perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery

Perception of respondents on usage of agricultural machinery	Frequently	Percent
Usage of agricultural machinery are too expensive		
Strongly Agree	10	15.38
Agree	27	41.54
Neutral	24	36.92
Strongly Disagree	4	6.15
Disagree	0	0.00
Agricultural machinery are not accessible		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	28	43.38
Neutral,	10	15.38
Strongly Disagree	14	21.54
Disagree	13	20.00
It is ment for only large scale farmers		
Strongly Agree	10	15.38
Agree	14	21.54
Neutral	24	36.92
Strongly Disagree	4	6.15
Disagree	13	20.00
It safes time		
Strongly Agree	10	15..38
Agree	18	27.69
Neutral	24	36.92
Strongly Disagree	8	12.31
Disagree	5	7.69
Tractor operator do cheat farmers		
Strongly Agree	0	0.00
Agree	5	7.69
Neutral	15	23.08
Strongly Disagree	28	43.08
Disagree	17	26.15

Source: Field survey, 2023.

sConclusion and Recommendation

It was concluded that most of the farmers do not know the right machinery to use and most of the farmers could not afford the use of agricultural mechanization due to its ex expensiveness. It was recommended that agricultural extension agents should educate farmers on the right machinery to use. Government should make agricultural machines affordable and accessible to farmers.

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